

**A STUDY ON EFFECT OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND
EMPLOYEE JOB SATISFACTION IN PREDICTING ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT
IN HOSPITAL**

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Abstract

The objective of this study was to identify the role of human resource management and employee job satisfaction in predicting organizational commitment in the healthcare sector. This study was done by quantitative survey research. In this study the independent variables are human resource management and employee job satisfaction and the dependent variable is organizational commitment. Human resource management is positively correlated with employee job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Both independent variables made significant contributions to the prediction of organizational commitment. As for the study convenient sampling is used hence the study have limited generalizability in other fields. This is cross-sectional study, there has to be caution in generalizing the results. Future Researchers may get more respondents from different geographical location. For this study questionnaire was used to collect the data however it is recommended that future researchers should use other methods such as personal interview or telephonic interview to collect the data. If there is a high level of job satisfaction among health care workers it will prevent low levels of turnover rate, absenteeism, levels of productivity and increase organizational commitment. HRM practices help in career development opportunities and better job opportunities. This study may suggest to ensure high levels of job satisfaction among employees and improved organizational commitment.

Keywords: Human Resource Management, Employee job satisfaction, Organizational commitment, Career development

Introduction

In the organizations, there is a report of its mission explaining that people are valuable resource. Any organization must have the right personnel at the right place and at the right time to achieve survive and achieve goal (Oladipo, 2011). All the organizations including Health care organizations are dependant on the quality and competence of its employees. Hence, organizations should pay much attention to their human resources as implementation of human resource practices helps in maximizing the employees' competencies in the organization (Saleem and Khurshid, 2014).

Human resource management may assist to develop the organizations characterized by intelligence, flexibility and competence as compared to their rivals. These organizations use various policies and practices of recruiting, selecting, training skilled employees. As a result employees will direct their efforts towards cooperation within the limited resources of their organization (Nancy,2013).

Also, the success, survival and competing potential of the organizations are linked with the commitment of their employees. If we want the commitment of the employees towards the organization then satisfaction of the employees is very important. Human resource management practices play a role in maintaining a mutual relationship between firms and their employees related to shared trust and duties. The employees offer their services to the organizations in exchange of perks received from the organization following the "social exchange theory" (Mehwish *et al.*, 2019).

Hence it is assumed the cost of employee turnover, absenteeism, low productivity can be minimized when the employees are satisfied and committed to their organization (Mizanur, Mohammad and Mohammad, 2012). The achievement of employees and their working capability are prerequisites of their sense of job satisfaction. The first priority of the organization should be employee job satisfaction and organization commitment to attract new competent employees and maintaining existing talented employees (Khera, 2010; Mizan *et al.*, 2013).

Literature review

HRM practices, job satisfaction and organizational commitment

The success of various organizations, such as hospitals, depend on the performance of their human resources (Uma *et al.*, 2017), which focus on employees' skills (Ong and Koh, 2018; Ong *et al.*, 2019). Human resource management practices can be considered as a set of internally coherent and consistent practices aimed at improving employee competence, motivation and commitment (Elrehail *et al.*, 2019). They also manage talent and skills to achieve organization's objectives (Ana *et al.*, 2019).

HRM practices help to create good working conditions and environment where employees are highly committed to the organization and do their best to achieve the organization's goals. Organizational commitment can be observed the employees' willingness to be committed to achieve the goal of the organization. The employees' level of identification, involvement and loyalty improves the organizational commitment (Devananda and Onahring, 2019). Employee job performance can be improved by good HRM practices (Faiza *et al.*, 2019).

HRM practices act as a good tool for increasing employees' job satisfaction (Mohammed *et al.*, 2019). Job satisfaction is an individual's inclination towards work roles that he/she is currently playing, and it is related to that individual's behavior in the workplace (Devananda and Onahring, 2019).

HRM practices help to improve the employees' commitment and their performance (Cai *et al.*, 2019). The organization is affected by the employee commitment and satisfaction (Elrehail *et al.*, 2019).

Ana *et al.* (2019) explained a direct relationship between HRM practices and employee satisfaction. Good HRM practices can improve employee satisfaction and commitment for the organization (Cai *et al.*, 2019). Employees' commitment is considered as bond to the organization (Mizan, *et al.*, 2013). If the employees are not committed and satisfied with their job it will lead to high rate of absenteeism (Murat *et al.*, 2014). In order to ensure employees' commitment, organization may use different motivation to boost up their commitment (Mehwish *et al.*, 2019). The mediating role of organizational commitment on the relationship between HRM practices and employee engagement was examined (Alima, Akhtar and Faizuniah Pangil, 2018). The results revealed that HRM practices were good predictors of employee engagement. Organizational commitment act as a partial mediator of HRM practices and employee engagement relationship concluded through the results.

HR policies helps in raising the level of job satisfaction among employees resulting high commitment of employees towards the organization (Prakash, 2017). Both are positively related with affective and normative commitment (Ambreen, 2011). Appropriate attitude and behaviours, job satisfaction, affective commitment and retention shows employees' commitment (Mohammad *et al.*, 2018). Abdirahman (2015) says there is a positive relationship between HRM practices and organizational commitment.

HRM practices helps in shaping worker behaviours and attitudes and affect the outcome of any organization (Norhasnina *et al.*, 2018)

(Abubakar *et al.*, 2017 a, b; Albrecht *et al.*, 2015; Ukil, 2016) found that HRM practices may lead to employee satisfaction and engagement. It was observed that there is a positive relationship between HRM practices, job satisfaction and organizational commitment (Murat *et al.*, 2014). (Mizan *et al.*, 2013) revealed that there were direct relationship among specific HR practices, job satisfaction and organizational commitment.

Problem Statement

Organizations face various challenges such as globalization, deregulation in different sectors. The changes helps to manage the staff businesses effectively in job satisfaction, employee performance and organizational commitment. It was evident that when employees were happy with their job, were successfully committed to their organizations and contributed to their effectiveness and the survival (Mahmood,2013). HRM practices have widely studied in connection with various organizational outcomes like employee job satisfaction, employee performance and employee commitment (Rahman *et al.*, 2013). There is no study on the role of HRM and employee job satisfaction in predicting organizational commitment.

Objectives of the study

1. To identify the relationship between and among HRM, employee job satisfaction and organizational commitment in the hospital.
2. To study the combined effects of HRM, employee job satisfaction on organizational commitment in the hospital.
3. To study the relative contribution of HRM, employee job satisfaction to organizational commitment in the hospital.

Significance of the study

This study may contribute to the literature on HRM, job satisfaction and organizational commitment in the hospitals. there is a rapid growth of hospital in India. Hence there is a requirement for recruiting efficient and experienced human resources (Mizan *et al.*, 2013). This study will help in the development of Indian hospital, which may lead to maintain this sector work effectively, leading to positive impact on the economy of India. It will also highlight the nature and importance of the HRM practices for the benefit of the banking sector.

H1: There is a positive correlation between HRM and employee job satisfaction.

H2: There is a positive correlation between job satisfaction and organizational commitment.

H3: There is a positive correlation between HRM and organizational commitment.

H4: There are combined effects of HRM and employee job satisfaction on organizational commitment.

H5: There is a contribution of HRM and employee job satisfaction to organizational commitment.

Research Methodology

Sample

Convenient sampling method was used to select the participants. Three hospitals of Uttarakhand were approached and selected to analyze the role of HRM and employee job satisfaction in predicting organizational commitment in the Hospital. The majority of the participants were between the ages of 23 and 29 years (n=180, 54.5%), 115 between 32 and 49 (34.8%), 35 between 50 and 59 (10.6%). As far as Educational qualification is concerned, most of the participants (93.9%) had a bachelors degree (n=310), 15 (4.5%) were holding paramedical degree and 5 (1.5%) were holding a master's degree. The work experience for the participants varied too; 120 (36.3) were between 5 to 10 years of experience, 190 (57.5%) were between 15 to 20 years of experience. Only 20 (6.2) were more than 20 years of experience. More than 500 questionnaires were distributed out of which 370 were received back, from which only 330 were selected, as they were filled correctly without missing questions. So, the final sample was 330 respondents from the three hospitals.

Design

The study was based on Quantitative survey research. HRM practices and employee job satisfaction are the independent variables and the dependent variable is organizational commitment.

Research Instrument

The questionnaire of HRM practices was used (Chandrakantan 2011). The questionnaire consists of 16 items, with a five point Likert Scale from 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree). The factor analysis gave a four- factor solution, namely, compensation policy, promotion policy, job security, and training and development, explaining 62.44% variance. Each factor consists of 4 items. The rating of item ranged from 1 to 5, and the composite score could range from 16 to 80. Cronbach's α was used to study the reliability of the scale in terms of internal consistency. The satisfactory level of internal consistency was demonstrated by the items. Different Cronbach's α value were 0.71 for compensation, 0.77 for promotion policy, 0.80 for job security, 0.75 for training and development.

The organizational commitment questionnaire was used (Norm, Cynthia and Francisco, 2017). The questionnaire calculated commitment in its normative dimension, which is based on reciprocity and responsibility as it value to the work in which there is a link to the organization based on faithfulness of workers set was developed (Norm *et al.*, 2017). The questionnaire consists of 30 items, with a five point Likert scale from 1 to 5. The score on each item ranged from 1 to 5, and the composite score could range from 30 to 150. The two factor solution, namely, loyalty reciprocity and compliance responsibility was yielded by factor analysis explaining 45.1% of variance. There was sufficient internal consistency, $\alpha= 0.85$.

Generic job satisfaction scale is used (Scott Macdonald and Peter MacIntyre, 1997). It is a reliable measure of a single construct. This questionnaire scale has 10 items, with a five point Likert scale from

1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Job stress, boredom, isolation and danger of illness or injury were the factors of this scale. The internal consistency reliability was shown by the items.

Cronbach's α value for the measure was 0.77. The scores on every item ranged from 1 to 5, and the composite score was from 5 to 50, higher scores indicated high job satisfaction.

Method

Before administering the scales, employees in the target hospitals were informed about the purpose of the study and they agreed to participate. They were communicated not to identify themselves in any way on the scale paper so that respondents respond honestly to the items. They were ensured that their responses and details will be kept confidential. All the entries were made in an SPSS file.

Data analysis

The tools used for data analysis were Pearson correlation and multiple regression. Multiple regression was used to analyze the contributions of HRM and employee job satisfaction to the prediction of organizational commitment in the Indian Hospitals.

Results

Descriptive data and inter-correlations

Table I

Descriptive statistics and inter-correlations of HRM, employee job satisfaction and organizational commitment

Variables	1	2	3
HRM	1.00		
Employee job satisfaction	0.688**	1.00	
Organizational commitment	0.524**	0.612**	1.00
Mean	70.27	122.34	48.53
SD	1.64	1.18	1.28

Note: ** $p < 0.01$

It shows the means, descriptive statistics and inter-correlations of HRM, employee job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Table I depicts that there are significant correlations between HRM, employee job satisfaction and organizational commitment. HRM correlates positively with employee job satisfaction ($r=0.688$) and organizational commitment ($r=0.524$). Employee job satisfaction was positively correlated with organizational commitment ($r = -0.612$).

HRM and employee job satisfaction as predictors of organizational commitment

Table II

The Regression results of the predictor variables (HRM and employee job satisfaction) and the outcome measure (organizational commitment) (model summary)^c

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	SE of the estimates
1	0.716 ^a	0.515	0.513	0.08585
2	0.758 ^b	0.573	0.571	0.08052

Note: ^aPredictors: (constant), HRM; ^bPredictors: (constant), HRM, EJS; ^cDependant variable: OC

The above figure depicted that the two independent variables (HRM and employee job satisfaction) when put together gave a coefficient of multiple regression (R) of 0.758 and a multiple correlation square of 0.571. It shows that 57.1 percent of the total variance in organizational commitment of those who participated in the study is accounted for by the combined effect of HRM and employee job satisfaction.

Table III

Summary of multiple regression analysis between the predictor variables (HRM and employee job satisfaction) and the outcome measure (organizational commitment) (ANOVA)^c.

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean square	F	Significance
1 Regression	2.555	1	2.555	346.651	0.000 ^a
Residual	2.418	328	0.007		
Total	4.973	329			
2 Regression	2.853	2	1.426	219.979	0.000 ^b
Residual	2.120	327	0.006		
Total	4.973	329			

Note: ^aPredictors: (constant), HRM; ^bPredictors: (constant), HRM, EJS; ^cDependant variable: OC

It indicates that the analysis of variance of the multiple regression data produced an F- ratio value significant at 0.01 level (F(2, 327)= 219.979; p<0.01).

Table IV

Relative contribution of the independent variables to the prediction of organizational commitment (coefficient)^a

Model	Unstandardized coefficients B	SE	Standardized coefficients β	t	Significance
I					
(Constant)	33.111	1.015		32.622	0.000
HRM	0.370	0.020	0.717	18.619	0.000
(Constant)	57.946	3.788	0.488	15.297	0.000
HRM	0.252	0.026	-0.335	9.856	0.000
EJS	-0.376	0.056		-6.773	0.000

Note: ^aDependant variable: OC

According to above Table each of the **independent variables made significant contribution to the prediction of organizational commitment. The results depicted that the following β weights**, which represented the relative contribution of the independent variables to the prediction, were observed. HRM (B=0.252, t=9.856; p<0.01) and employee job satisfaction (B=0.376, t=6.773; p<0.01). Although the two variables made significant relative contribution to the prediction of organizational commitment, employee job satisfaction is a good predictor.

Discussion

The purpose of the study was to investigate the combined effects of HRM and employee job satisfaction (predictor variables) on organizational commitment (outcome measure). The purpose is to investigate the relative contribution of HRM and employee job satisfaction to organizational commitment in the Indian Hospital. In addition the aim was to identify if there were correlations between and among HRM, employee job satisfaction and organizational commitment in the Indian Hospitals. The findings extend our knowledge on the relationship between HRM, employee job satisfaction and organizational commitment in the Indian Hospitals.

Findings from Table I shows that HRM is correlated with employee job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Employee job satisfaction was found to be positively correlated with organizational commitment. These findings were consistent with previous studies highlighting that human resource practice and employee job satisfaction were found to be positively related to employees' organizational commitment. (Haruna and Marthandan, 2017; Nwachukwu and Chladkova, 2017; Taghrid, 2015). It is likely that employees' positive perceptions about the human resource practice increase their job satisfaction and commitment to their organization.

The purpose of HRM is to ensure that the organization is able to achieve success through manpower. HRM gives the organization with required capabilities that allow its people to learn and use new opportunities. It is concernec with achieving the organizational effectiveness, human capital management, knowledge management, reward management, employee relations and meeting different needs (Osibanio, 2012).

The results of this study is consistent with the findings of Ali *et al.* 's (2019), revealed that job satisfaction was correlated with organizational commitment. In addition HRM provides suitable for increasing employee satisfaction and job motivation by giving awards based on the actual evaluation of performance and increasing salary in accordance to employees' capabilities, aiming to improve their organizational commitment.

The high level of job satisfaction of employees is concerned with high levels of productivity, low level of turnover rate, low level of absenteeism and levels of organizational commitment. HRM practices provide opportunities and effective growth and development of human resources in the organization, are a stronger predictor of organizational commitment. While, the absence of career development opportunities and good job opportunities are important reasons for employee turnover intention (Budhwar *et al.*, 2009).

The results of this study are consistent with those of Edgar and Geare's (2005), revealing that HRM practices would influence employee attitude. Job satisfaction can be achieved through equitable rewards system such as pay, working conditions, training and development and fair HR practices (Osibanio *et al.*, 2012).

As per the results of regression analysis two independent variables (HRM and employee job satisfaction) when combined together yielded a coefficient of multiple regression (R) of 0.574 and a multiple correlation square of 0.571. This showed that 57.1 percent of the total variance in organizational commitment of those who participated in the study was accounted for by the combination of HRM and employee job satisfaction.

Applications

The findings of this study has the practical implications. Low level of turnover rate, absenteeism can be prevented by high level of employee job satisfaction. It may also help in increasing the level of productivity and career development opportunities. We can recommend to ensure high levels of job satisfaction among employees and enhanced organizational commitment by implementing good HR practices.

Conclusion

The objective of this study was to identify the combined effects of HRM and employee job satisfaction (predictor variables) on organizational commitment (outcome measure). The aim was to find out if there were correlations between and among HRM and employee job satisfaction to organizational commitment in Indian Hospitals. It was found that employee job satisfaction correlated positively with organizational commitment. It can be said that the HR practices, policies are means through which organizational people can be managed to gain competitive advantage. It is well known that the health care sector has both dynamic and competitive nature, so innovative HRM practices which may provide employee with new and diverse skills and cognition may be implemented.

Limitation & future Research

First limitation was the convenient sampling method for collecting the data. Hence the findings of the study have limited generalizability in other regions and age groups. Second, as a cross-sectional study, there has to be caution in making any generalizability of the results. Future Researchers may get more respondents from wider geographical locations. In this study self-report questionnaires were used to collect the data from respondents. It is recommended that future researchers use different methods such as personal interview, observation method etc to collect the data.

References

Abdirahman, S. (2015), “*Human resource management practices and organizational commitment*”, International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management, Vol. 8 No. 3, pp. 156-193.

Abubakar, A.M., Elrehail, H., Alatailat, M.A. and Elçi, A. (2017a), “*Knowledge management, decision-making style and organizational performance*”, Journal of Innovation and Knowledge, Vol. 4 No. 2, pp. 104-114, doi: 10.1016/J.JIK.2017.07.003.

Abubakar, A M., Namin, B H., Harazneh, I., Arasli, H. and Tunç, T. (2017b), “*Does gender moderates the relationship between favoritism/nepotism, supervisor incivility, cynicism and workplace withdrawal: a neural network and SEM approach*”, Tourism Management Perspectives, Vol. 23, pp. 129–139, doi: 10.1016/j.tmp.2017.06.001.

Albrecht, S.L., Bakker, A.B., Gruman, J.A., Macey, W.H. and Saks, A.M. (2015), “*Employee engagement, human resource management practices and competitive advantage*”, Journal of Organizational Effectiveness: People and Performance, Vol. 2 No. 1, pp. 7-35, doi: 10.1108/JOEPP-08-2014-0042.

Ali, E., Fahimeh, R., Fatemeh, M. and Reza, M. (2019), “*Prediction of organizational commitment based on job satisfaction dimensions among employees of the ministry of health and medical education*”, Caspian Journal of Health Research, Vol. 4 No. 2, pp. 49-53.

Alima, A.k. and Faizuniah, P. (2018), “*Mediating role of organizational commitment in the relationship between human resource management practices and employee engagement*”, International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy, Vol. 38 Nos 7/8, pp. 606-636, doi: 10.1108/IJSSP-08-2017-0097.

Altarawneh, I. (2009), “*Training and development evaluation in Jordanian banking organizations*”, Research and Practice in Human Resource Management (RPHRM), Singapore publisher, Vol. 17 No. 1, pp. 1-23.

Ambreen, M. (2011), “*Impact of implied organizational support on organizational commitment*”, European Journal of Business and Management, Vol. 3 No. 11, pp. 41-45.

Ana, C., Gisela, D. and Tatiane, P. (2019), “*Do human resources policies and practices produce resilient public servants? Evidence of the validity of a structural model and measurement models*”, Revista Brasileira de Gestao de Negocios, Vol. 21 No. 1, pp. 70-85, doi: 10.7819/rbgn.v21i1.3965.

Budhwar, P.S., Varma, A., Malhotra, N. and Mukherjee, A. (2009), “*Insights into the Indian call centre industry: can internal marketing help tackle high employee turnover?*”, Journal of Services Marketing, Vol. 23, pp. 351-362, doi: 10.1108/08876040910973459.

Cai, L., Shumaila, N., Muhammad, A., Basil, K. and Majid, M. (2019), “*An empirical investigation on the relationship between a high-performance work system and employee performance: measuring a*

mediation model through partial least squares–structural equation modeling”, *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, Vol. 12, pp. 397-416.

Chandrakantan, S., Faridahwati, M. and Shamsudin, H. (2011), “*Linking human resource practices and organisational performance: evidence from small and medium organisations in Malaysia*”, *Jurnal Pengurusan*, Vol. 32, pp. 27-37.

Choi, J. and Lee, K. (2013), “*Effects of employees' perceptions on the relationship between HR practices and firm performance for Korean firms*”, *Personnel Review*, Vol. 42 No. 5, pp. 573-594.

Devananda, S. and Onahring, B. (2019), “*Entrepreneurial intention, job satisfaction and organisation commitment - construct of a research model through literature review*”, *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, Vol. 9 No. 16, doi: 10.1186/s40497-018-0134-2.

Edgar, F. and Geare, A. (2005), “*HRM practice and employee attitudes: different measure-different result*”, *Personnel Review*, Vol. 34 No. 5, pp. 534-549.

Elrehail, H., Harazneh, I., Abuhjeeleh, M., Alzghoul, A., Alnajdawi, S. and Ibrahim, H. (2019), “*Employee satisfaction, human resource management practices and competitive advantage*”, *European Journal of Management and Business Economics*, ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print, doi: 10.1108.

Faiza, M., Wei, L., Bányai, T., Nurunnabi, M. and Subhan, Q.A. (2019), “*An examination of sustainable HRM practices on JobPerformance: an application of training as a moderator*”, *Sustainability*, Vol. 11, p. 2263, doi: 10.3390/su11082263.

Haruna, A.Y. and Marthandan, G. (2017), “*Foundational competencies for enhancing work engagement in SMEs Malaysia*”, *Journal of Workplace Learning*, Vol. 29 No. 3, pp. 165-184.

Khera, S.N. (2010), “*Human resource practices and their impact on employee productivity: a perceptual analysis of private, public and foreign bank employees in India*”, *DSM Business Review*, Vol. 2 No. 1, pp. 65-86.

Mahmood, A. (2013), “*Evaluation of the degree to which employee satisfaction is related to internal marketing within pakistani universities*”, (Unpublished doctoral thesis), University of Salford, Salford.

Mehwish, J., Abeera, A., Aideded, B. and Tania, H. (2019), “*Human resource practices and organizational commitment: the mediating role of job satisfaction in emerging economy*”, *Cogent Business and Management*, Vol. 6, p. 1608668, doi: 10.1080/23311975.2019.1608668.

Mizanur, R., Mohammad, J. and Mohammad, A. (2013), “*The role of human resource management practices on job satisfaction and organizational commitment in banking sector of Bangladesh- A comparative analysis*”, *Journal of Faculty of Business Administration (JFBA)*, Part-C, Vol. 9 Nos 1/2, pp. 1-13.

Mohammad, R., Rubelad, N., Newaz, R., Yuslizac, D. and Mui, H. (2018), "*High commitment human resource management practices and employee service behaviour: trust in management as mediator*", IIMB Management Review, Vol. 30 No. 4, pp. 316-329.

Mohammed, S., Yap, V. and Chan, K. (2019), "*The effect of HRM practices and employees' job satisfaction on employee performance*", Management Science Letters, Vol. 9, pp. 771-786.

Murat, K., Mustafa, F. and Turgay, S. (2014), "*Human resource management practices, job satisfaction and organizational commitment*", International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences, Vol. 4 No. 9, pp. 178-190.

Nadarajah, S., Kadiresan, V., Kumar, N., Kamil, A. and Yusff, Y.M. (2012), "*The relationship of HR practices of academicians toward Career development in Malaysian private higher institutions*", Procedia-Social and Behavioral sciences, Vol. 57, pp. 102-118.

Nancy, Q. (2013), "*The impact of hrm practices on organizational performance: the case study of some selected rural banks*", A thesis submitted to the Department of Managerial Science, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology.

Norhasnina, M., Dato Mohamad, N. and Wan, N. (2018), "*The effects of human resources management (hrm) practices on employee performance with the mediating role of employee engagement: preparing for industrial revolution 4.0*", 1st National Conference on Multidisciplinary Research and Practice, 2018.

Norm, B., Rodríguez-Loredo, C.S. and Paz-Rodríguez, F. (2017), "*Development and validation of a questionnaire on normative organizational commitment: a pilot study in Mexicans workers*", Anales de Psicología, Vol. 33 No. 2, pp. 393-402.

Nwachukwu, C.E. and Chladková, H. (2017), "*Human resource management practices and employee satisfaction in microfinance banks in Nigeria*", Trends Economics and Management, Vol. 11 No. 28, pp. 23-35.

Oladipo, J.A. and Abdalkader, D.S. (2011), "*Strategic human resource management and organizational performance in the Nigerian manufacture sector: an empirical investigation*", International Journal of Business and Management, Vol. 6 No. 9, doi: 10.5539/ijbm.v6n9p46.

Ong, C.H. and Koh, R.J. (2018), "*The influence of human resources management practices on employee performance in the manufacturing sector in Malaysia*", International Journal of Human Resources Studies, Vol. 8 No. 2, pp. 129-147.

Ong, C., Maria, A., lee, P., Kowang, O. and Chin, F. (2019), "*The relationship between human resource management practices and job performance in the courier service industry*", International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences, Vol. 9 No. 3, pp. 63-79.

Osibanjo, O., Kehinde, O. and Abiodun, A. (2012), “*Human resource management and employee job satisfaction: evidence from the Nigerian banking industry*”, Journal of Economics and Business Research, Vol. 1, pp. 17-32.

Paşaoğlu, D. and Tonus, H.Z. (2014), “*Strategic importance of human resource practices on job satisfaction in private hospitals*”, Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences, Vol. 150, pp. 394-403, doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.09.035.

Prakash, K. (2017), “*Issue of organizational commitment : evidence from Nepalese banking industry*”, Management Dynamics, Vol. 20 No. 1, pp. 119-129.

Rahman, M.M., Uddin, M.J. and Miah, M.S. (2013), “*The role of human resource management practices on job satisfaction and organizational commitment in banking sector of Bangladesh- A comparative analysis*”, Journal of the Faculty of Business Administration JFBA), Islamic University Studies, Vol. 10 No. 1, pp. 270-275.

Saleem, I. and Khurshid, A. (2014), “*Do human resource practices affect employee performance?*”, Pakistan Business Review, Vol. 15 No. 4, pp. 669-688.

Scott, M. and Peter, M. (1997), “*The generic job satisfaction scale: scale development and its correlates*”, Employee Assistance Quarterly, Vol. 13 No. 2, pp. 1-16.

Suifan, T S. (2015), “*The effect of human resources practices on organizational commitment: a Jordanian study*”, Journal of Management Research, Vol. 7 No. 4, pp. 222-232.

Ukil, M.I. (2016), “*The impact of employee empowerment on employee satisfaction and service quality: empirical evidence from financial enterprises in Bangladesh*”, Verslas: Teorija Ir Praktika, Vol. 17 No. 2, pp. 178-189, doi: 10.3846/btp.2016.651.

Uma, S., Aurolipy and Madhusmita, D. (2017), “*Impact of hrm practices on job satisfaction and performance: an empirical study in health care sector*”, International Journal of Economic Research, Vol. 14 No. 2, pp. 95-105.